

Implementation of Adaptive Arrays in the Block Oriented Systems Simulator

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Abstract

This study investigated the feasibility of implementing adaptive array algorithms in a simulation program called the Block Oriented Systems Simulator (BOSS). Two algorithms in particular were used: the least mean square (LMS) algorithm in real and complex form originally developed by Widrow, et. al. and the Applebaum algorithm. Two arrays were simulated with simple isotropic radiators used as the array elements. The first array used two elements spaced one half wavelength apart. The second array used four elements with variable geometry. The approach taken was to first implement the algorithms and arrays in the simulation language. Testing the algorithms with simple inputs and checking the algorithms ability to track these inputs was the second step. The last step was to test the algorithms with the arrays. The results of the simulations showed the LMS algorithms implemented in BOSS were able to track DC signals along with sinusoidal inputs. The BOSS LMS implementation was also able to reject jammer signals by changing the gain and phase of the array elements. The amount of signal-to-jammer ratio was only a function of the gain limits put on the LMS loops. The Applebaum algorithm was used with a sidelobe canceller circuit with one adaptive weight. This implementation provided weight convergence with nulls being placed at a jammer's spatial location. The null depth exactly matched the jammer power. The simulations from this study show that adaptive array algorithms can be implemented and simulated with BOSS. The BOSS simulation environment proved to be an excellent tool for prototyping systems along with providing a rich selection of post simulation output products.

Background

Numerous studies have been performed on adaptive antenna arrays [2, 1-271]. By implementing different array patterns or spacings with different adaptive algorithms, various types of performance are achieved. In almost every case, some type of simulation was performed to predict the performance of the array and the adaptation algorithm. A common approach to the simulation is to model the array and algorithm in some high order language such as FORTRAN. This approach requires each element in the adaptive antenna be broken down into its smallest mathematical entity. These entities are then assembled and the simulation built from the bottom up, going from the model of the simplest resistor to the array and its environment.

A second approach to system simulation is to use a computer to simulate waveforms that flow through the system [3, 1-1]. Such a system is the Block Oriented Systems Simulator (BOSS). The BOSS environment utilizes a set of templates for most elements used by communications engineers. The designer recalls these templates, fills in the necessary parameters, and builds a circuit or system from the "block" level rather than the component level. The designer can then evaluate the performance of the design from within the BOSS environment through built-in simulation tools. BOSS also provides many display options for simulation results through a post processor function. The BOSS graphics software that is presented to the user is written in LISP. BOSS then translates the user-entered block diagram into a FORTRAN simulation program [3, 1-3]. Primitive modules not implemented in BOSS can be built in FORTRAN and then imported as a BOSS template. Because BOSS was originally written to simulate communication systems, this feature allows a system designer to implement almost any circuit desired.

An adaptive array might also be modeled from the block level rather than a component

level in order to perform a simulation. One of the most common algorithms for adaptation is the Least Mean Square (LMS) algorithm. It can be broken down into integrators, summers, amplifiers, and time delays. The antenna elements themselves might be modeled as amplifiers with phase shifts dependent on their relative spacing. This approach could lead to modeling adaptive arrays in a block fashion.

This work investigated implementing adaptive antenna arrays within the Block Oriented Systems Simulator (BOSS). Specifically, two different adaptive algorithms along with two different arrays were investigated to determine their suitability for block type simulation. Once the algorithms and the arrays were implemented in BOSS, results from simulations in this system were compared with results of theoretical studies in the literature.

Theory

Since the late 1960s and early 1970s, a number of techniques for controlling adaptive antenna arrays have been developed. The concept of the adaptive array is to adjust the array weights in some way to enhance signal reception. This generally means enhancing the desired signal while reducing the effect of noise through a weight adjustment algorithm. The noise can be an interference source such as a jammer or simply thermal noise.

The most significant work on adaptive array algorithms began with the publication of the Widrow, Mantey, Griffith and Goode development of the least mean squares (LMS) algorithm for adaptive antenna systems [4, 6]. Another technique developed in 1966 but not published in the open literature until 1976 was the Applebaum algorithm [1, 585]. A number of other techniques have been developed including the power inversion algorithm, direct matrix inversion, and the update covariance matrix inverse algorithm [2, 37]. In each algorithm, there is

an attempt to enhance the desired signal while reducing the effects of noise.

In the LMS algorithm, the weights are updated according to the following recursive equation [9, 2149]:

$$\mathbf{W}_{j+1} = \mathbf{W}_j + 2\mu e_j \mathbf{X}_j \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{W} is the weight vector of N weights w_1, w_2, \dots, w_N , j is the iteration number, e_j is the difference between the output and the desired signals, μ is a convergence factor, and \mathbf{X}_j is the input vector of N inputs x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N at iteration j . There is a continuous representation of Eq (1) given by:

$$\mathbf{W}(t) = 2\mu \int_0^t e(\tau) \mathbf{X}(\tau) d\tau \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{W}(t)$ is the weight vector of N weights $w_1(t), w_2(t), \dots, w_N(t)$, μ is a convergence factor, $e(\tau)$ is the difference between the output and desired signals, and $\mathbf{X}(\tau)$ is again the input vector of N inputs. Finally, there is a complex form given by [10, 719-720]:

$$\mathbf{W}_{j+1} = \mathbf{W}_j + 2\mu e_j \bar{\mathbf{X}}_j \quad (3)$$

where the weight and input vectors are along with the error signal, e_j , are now complex entities with all operations obeying the rules of complex algebra. The overbar on the input vector, $\bar{\mathbf{X}}_j$, indicates the complex conjugate.

The very compact form of Eqs (1) and (3) are easily implemented in a digital computer. The LMS algorithm requires a desired signal. The presence of the desired signal in the circuit should remove the need to go through this process at all. The key here is that the desired signal does not have to be an exact replica of what the system is expecting. The desired signal has only to be correlated with the expected input and uncorrelated with the noise. The receiver expecting the signal could produce the desired signal. This replica signal might not be in phase

with the input signal but should be correlated with the input. Compton presents several other techniques for producing the desired signal as a function of the input [4, 396-431].

The LMS algorithm attempts to minimize the mean square error between a desired signal and the system output. When the weights have adapted to an optimum point, the desired signal is enhanced and the noise reduced. The overall result is improved signal-to-noise ratio. There are times when the desired signal is unknown. However, there is still a need to improve the signal to noise ratio by reducing the effects of interference sources. The Applebaum algorithm does not require the desired signal and can be used in this case (2:47).

Like the LMS algorithm, the Applebaum algorithm adjusts the weights of an adaptive array in an attempt to maximize the signal-to-noise ratio [4, 47]. The antenna pattern produced by the adaptation process places antenna nulls in the direction of noise sources. The weights in the Applebaum system are updated according to the following equation [1, 593]:

$$w_k(t) = G[\bar{t}_k(t) - \int_0^t x_k(\tau) \sum_{i=1}^n w_i(\tau) x_i(\tau) d\tau] \quad (4)$$

where w_k and w_i are the i th and k th weights, x_i is the i th input signal, \bar{t}_k is the signal modulation seen by the k th array element, and G is a arbitrary constant. There is also a discrete form of Eq (4) given by [6, 1696]:

$$w_i(j+1) = w_i(j) + \gamma \mu \bar{t}_i - \gamma \bar{x}_i(j) s(j) \quad (5)$$

where w_i is the i th of N weights, j is the iteration number, γ and μ are constants, $\bar{x}_i(j)$ is the complex conjugate of the i th input at the j th iteration, and $s(j)$ is the summed outputs of all array elements.

The key to this approach is that there is no need for the desired signal. If the desired signal is missing, the algorithm still attempts to remove the undesired noise.

Implementing the Algorithms

For each algorithm given by Eqs (1) through (5) there are equivalent block diagrams. For instance, Eq (2) requires two multipliers, an integrator, and a gain factor of 2μ . BOSS provides two and three input multipliers in the arithmetic section of its *Basic Building Blocks*. The gain coefficient is provided in the *Basic Building Blocks* as a module called *REAL COEFFICIENT GAIN*. BOSS also has an integrator in its filter section. Putting these modules together yields an analog LMS loop. The BOSS implementation is shown in Figure (1). The block diagram in Figure (1) was produced with the *BOSS Print Module Block Diagram* command. The two small triangles which point in at the bottom and left side of the diagram are inputs to the circuit and are labeled I# 1 and I# 2. Input 1 is the loop input from the array element feeding this particular LMS loop while input 2 is the error formed by the difference between the desired signal and the system output. The error signal will be formed at a higher level and fed back to this part of the circuit. The two outputs are labeled O# 1 and O# 2 and are the loop output and the weight value. The outputs are on the right side of the block diagram and are represented by triangles that point out of the circuit. Output 1 is simply $w_i(t)x_i(t)$. The weight value is output so that a time history of the weight's behavior is available. The *REAL COEFF GAIN* represents the 2μ convergence factor and is exported from this level of circuit abstraction as an adjustable parameter.

Using the same approach for the discrete implementation as for the analog implementation, the two multipliers and adder from the *Basic Building Blocks* were used. A unit delay is available in BOSS's *Memory* section of the *Basic Building Blocks*. The same gain coefficient was used to provide the 2μ factor. The BOSS imple-

mentation is shown in Figure (2). The inputs and outputs to this loop are the same as in Figure (1).

The Complex LMS algorithm along with Applebaum algorithm discrete and continuous forms were implemented using the same approach. The only other module needed was one to form a complex conjugate. This module is available in BOSS's *Basic Building Blocks*.

Array Implementation

With the algorithms implemented, the next step is to implement the two and four element arrays. Figure (3) shows a two element array with a desired signal arriving at angle θ_d with reference to element 1. The two elements are spaced $\lambda/2$ apart where λ is the wavelength of the center frequency of the desired signal as well as the array wavelength. The desired signal will arrive at element 2 at a different time than at element 1. This causes a phase shift between the signals at the two elements. In the case of Figure (3), the phase shift is given by the equation [4, 24]:

$$\phi = \pi \sin(\theta_d) \quad (6)$$

The difference in arrival time and phase shift for this array is applicable to any signal whether it is the desired, a jammer, or a noise source. To implement the array in Figure (3) using BOSS, the array was broken into three different parts. The first part processed the desired signal. If element 1 is used as a reference, the signal seen by element 1 should simply be passed through the array to the signal processing section. This is accomplished with a unity gain element. The signal received from element 2 should have a phase shift in accordance with Eq (6). For real signals, BOSS provides a phase parameter in its sinusoidal source only. However, the phase parameter could be provided as a time delay within the array implementation. To provide the correct phase shift, the incoming signal is delayed

an appropriate number of time samples. BOSS provides a multi-sample delay in its *Memory* section of the *Basic Building Blocks*. The module is called *Multi-Stage Delay*. Using the delay element along with a constant gain module, the signal section of the array was constructed within BOSS and is shown in Figure (4). The jammer and noise sections were implemented in the same fashion. The array itself is now formed by combining the three sections. The element 1 outputs of the signal, jammer, and noise sections are added together to form the total element 1 output of the array. The element 2 outputs from the three sections are also added together to form the total element 2 output. The resulting array is shown in Figure (5). Any number of array elements can be implemented using this technique. The delay for each element is computed to provide the appropriate phase shift. For complex signals, the input and output ports of the arrays must be complex. To handle both complex and real signals, BOSS allows inputs and outputs to be untyped with the type being determined at simulation time. Using this approach, the arrays can handle either real or complex signals.

LMS Algorithm Tests

The first step in testing the LMS algorithm implementation in BOSS, as with other algorithm implementations, was to build a simple test circuit in BOSS. A sinusoid or DC signal could be used as the input to the LMS loop. The same input signal could also be routed into an amplifier or attenuator and then used as the desired signal. After adaptation, the weight value should match the amplifier's setting thereby modifying the input signal to match the desired signal. The BOSS implementation of such a test circuit is shown in Figure (6). In this circuit, the module labeled *REAL COEFF GAIN* at the top of the circuit is an amplifier that will modify the sinusoidal input to form the desired signal. The

second gain module is set to a constant -1 to subtract the output of the loop from the desired signal to form the error out of the adder. The *UNIT DELAY* module is inserted in the feedback path to take into account that the error signal cannot be feedback instantaneously. (BOSS will not allow a 0 time delay in a feedback path.) This module simply delays the feedback for one simulation iteration. Its output is initially set to 0. The module labeled *SINK* is used to provide a path for the monitored weight value. The LMS loop should adapt to match the gain of the amplifier during the simulation.

During simulations with the test circuit in Figure (6), the convergence factor of the LMS loop, the amplifier gain factor, and the sinusoid's frequency, phase, and amplitude were exported as simulation parameters. Exporting these parameters allowed them to be varied during different simulations in order to observe the loops performance without constantly changing the circuit itself. A representative result for the weight behavior of the LMS test circuit of Figure (6) is shown in Figure (7). With μ set to 0.1, the weight adapted to 0.5 in 1.1 seconds when the input was a 5 Hertz (Hz) sinusoid. The final weight result was exactly as expected with the desired amplitude at 1/2 of the input signal. Since the output was a duplicate of the desired signal, the error converged to 0 within the 1.1 seconds. The entire experiment was repeated for 5 KHz, 5 MHz and 5 GHz sinusoids. The results show the same adaptation behavior but scaled by time. This result indicated that the discrete LMS loop contains no frequency dependent components. Whenever this LMS loop was used in a circuit, there was justification for operating at lower frequencies since the results can be translated to higher frequencies.

The next step involved varying the convergence factor μ . Decreasing the convergence factor should lead to a smoother convergence of the weight while actual convergence takes longer. In

the first test, μ was reduced for 0.1 to 0.05. As Figure (8) shows, convergence time did increase to approximately 2.5 seconds. However, the convergence was smoother. The convergence factor was then increased to 0.5. The weight value did converge faster. Convergence took approximately 0.4 seconds versus 1.1 seconds when μ was set to 0.1 and 2.5 seconds with μ set to 0.05. However, there was a 0.1 overshoot which represents 20 percent of the weights final value. Increasing the convergence factor does increase the speed of convergence but at the price of overshoot. This type of behavior is exactly what is to be expected for an LMS loop. For a similar circuit, Compton shows weight convergence in approximately 100 samples with μ set at 0.1 [4, 71]. For convergence in 1.1 seconds shown in Figure (7), 110 samples were taken. The same reference showed convergence in 35 samples when μ was increased to 0.5. For this implementation, the weight converged in 40 samples when sampling at 100 samples per second. In both cases, the simulation produced by BOSS agreed closely with Compton's results.

For all the testing at various frequencies and values of the convergence factors, the BOSS implementation of the discrete LMS loop adapted to produce the desired output. The implementation of the loop and testing through simulation were easier than if the experiments has been programmed in a high order computer language. The same tests were run with the continuous-time LMS implementation shown in Figure (2). The results closely matched the discrete results and are not duplicated here.

Two Element Array Testing

With the BOSS LMS circuit tested, the next step was construction of a two element array system. The LMS loop in Figure (2) along with the two element array in Figure (5) were combined with other BOSS modules to form the system in Figure (9). The top sinusoid input on the left

side acts as the transmitter the system is trying to receive. The sinusoid near the upper right part of the system represents the desired signal. The sinusoid on the system's left acts as a tone jammer. The Gaussian random generator acts as a noise source. The two multi-stage delays are used in the system to provide the 90 degrees of phase shift needed to form the quadrature component of the loop inputs. The modules labeled *SINK* are used as a monitoring point for the weight values during simulation.

The two element array LMS system was first tested with a 5 Hz sinusoid as the transmitter and the desired signal. The transmitter is broadside to the array. A BOSS simulation parameter is the time between samples, (DT). In order to meet the Nyquist criterion of having the sampling frequency at least twice the highest frequency in the circuit, DT can be as great as 0.1 seconds for the 5 Hz input. However, with 0.1 seconds between samples, 2.5 samples must be used to provide the 90 degrees of phase shift for the quadrature weights. The number of samples to delay in the multi-stage delays must be an integer. To achieve any integer degree phase shift, the sampling frequency must be higher (that is, DT must be smaller). By raising the sampling frequency to 1800 Hz (DT lowered to $5.55E-4$), each sample delay represents one degree of phase delay. To get 90 degrees of phase delay, the multi-stage delay was set to 90 samples. As can be seen in the weight plot in Figure (10), the system converged in 0.5 seconds. Since the input signal arrives at each array element with no relative phase shift, the inphase elements should track the signal with the quadrature elements going to 0. This is exactly what happened. The gain in the direction of the source was 1, with each element providing 1/2 of the output. The convergence time of 0.5 seconds, (or 900 samples), again agrees within 5 percent of the convergence time of a two element system [4, 71].

The final test of the two element array sys-

tem involved including a tone jammer. The jammer was simply a sinusoid at 4 Hz. A phase shift was provided for the jammer by providing a delay in the signal at the second array element. The source was placed at 0 degrees and the jammer at 30 degrees relative to the array. Since there was an overall increase in power entering the array, the convergence factor had to be reduced from 0.1 to 0.005 to prevent divergence of the error and output signals. The two element array only achieved approximately a 3 dB suppression of the jammer signal. This number agrees closely with the suppression obtained with a two element array [4, 37].

Complex LMS Algorithm Testing

A complex LMS test circuit was implemented using the complex LMS loop module. BOSS provides a complex tone generator module in its *ANALOG SOURCES* section and this tone generator was used as the input to the LMS loop. The amplitude of the desired signal was produced by passing the input through a gain module where the gain was a simulation time parameter. The desired signal phase was formed by multiplying the input signal by a complex exponential. The complex exponential phase was constant, provided by a generator which had a value set as a parameter at simulation time. Multiplying the input by the weight value, forming the error, and providing feedback were accomplished in a fashion similar to previous test circuits. The complex LMS test circuit is shown in Figure (11).

The complex weight real and imaginary components in Figure (11) adapted to 0.5 and 0.0 when the input signal was multiplied by 0.5 with no phase shift to form the desired signal. When 30 degrees of phase were added to the input, the real component of the weight adapted to 0.433 while the imaginary component adapted to 0.25.

This produced a 30 degree phase shift of the input and a reduction of the input's magnitude to 0.5. The complex test circuit showed that the complex LMS loop adapted to simple inputs where the amplitude and phase of the desired signal were not the same as the input.

Complex Four Element Array Testing

A four element array system capable of handling complex signals was implemented. The array inputs were two complex tones, one acting as the transmitter and the other as a tone jammer, and complex white noise. All three sources are available in BOSS's *ANALOG SOURCES* section. After both complex tones, a gain module was added to provide attenuation of the input and jammer signals. Each of the array's four outputs were fed into a complex LMS loop and then multiplied by the loop's output which is a complex weight. The weighted array outputs were all summed to form the adapted array output. An error signal was again formed by subtracting a desired complex tone from the adapted array output. The error was then fed back to each complex LMS loop.

A simulation was performed with the source at 0 degrees and a jammer at 30 degrees. The desired signal was a complex tone at 5 Hz with no phase shift for this simulation. The 20 dB tone jammer operating at 4 Hz was placed at 30 degrees clockwise referenced to the upper left array element of a square array with the elements placed $\lambda/2$ wavelengths apart. The weights again adapted to produce an output which is a reproduction of the desired signal. However, the weights took almost 1 second to adapt because the convergence factor had to be reduced when the power increased at the array input. The signal-to-noise ratio was improved by 20 dB.

Applebaum Algorithm Testing

The BOSS Applebaum loop implementation was tested using a sidelobe canceller circuit suggested by Gabriel [5, 242]. The test arrangement is shown in Figure (12).

A complex tone source is added to a complex white noise source to form the block labeled *Source + Noise*. This block's output acts as a tone jammer with noise. Each channel also has uncorrelated complex white noise added to simulate channel noise. The output of the top channel signal is added to the bottom channel output to form the sidelobe canceller output. The bottom channel input is multiplied by the complex weight formed by the block labeled *Complex Applebaum Loop*. The array output and the t_k component are fed into the loop along with the bottom channel input. All input signals are lowpass filtered to simulate the passband of a receiver. To test this circuit, a tone jammer 20 dB above the channel noise was placed at 10 degrees relative to broadside of the array. The steering vector, t_k , was set to a desired look direction of zero degrees. The input cutoff frequency was set to 5 MHz. Using these numbers, the complex weight should adapt to an optimal value of $0.96e^{j148^\circ}$ [5, 246]. The weight converged to a value of 1.0 with a phase of 148 degrees as shown in Figures (13) and (14). The array gain plot in Figure (15) shows a 21 dB null at 10 degrees which is the location of the jammer. The theoretical value from Gabriel [5, 246] produces an infinitely deep null at 10 degrees. But as Compton mentions, the nulls are only as deep as the jammer power [4, 38]. The simulation results for the discrete Applebaum loop match closely the theoretical predictions.

Summary

The LMS algorithm implementation in BOSS was successfully tested in a test circuit, two el-

ement array, and four element array. The complex LMS algorithm implementation in BOSS was also successfully tested in a test circuit and four element complex array. The Applebaum algorithm implemented in BOSS produced simulation weight and array pattern results which closely matched theoretical predictions.

Considering the objective of studying the feasibility of implementing adaptive arrays in BOSS, this effort met with success. BOSS provides the necessary modules to theoretically implement most adaptive arrays. If a needed module does not exist in the BOSS library, the module can be implemented in FORTRAN and imported to BOSS. The BOSS simulation environment provides the necessary tools to simulate arrays and adaptive algorithms. The amount of effort needed to perform the simulations was greatly reduced during this study by being able to implement needed sections in a block fashion.

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References

- [1] Applebaum, Sidney P. "Adaptive Arrays," IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation, AP-24, 5, 585-598 (September 1976).
- [2] Bar-ness, Y. and Pickholtz, R. "Tutorial: Adaptive Array Processing and Interference Cancellation," MILCOM 1988.
- [3] Block Oriented Systems Simulator, BOSS, User's Guide, COMDISCO Corporation, January 1989.

- [4] Compton, R. T. Adaptive Antennas, Concepts and Performance, Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey: Prentice Hall, 1988.
- [5] Gabriel, Willaim F. "Adaptive Arrays - An Introduction," Proceedings of the IEEE, 64, Number 2, 239-272, (February 1976).
- [6] Griffiths, L.J. "A Simple Adaptive Algorithm for Real-Time Processing in Antenna Arrays," Proceedings of the IEEE, 57, Number 10, 1696, (October 1969).
- [7] Pipes, Louis A. and Havanessian, Shahan A. Matrix Computer Methods in Engineering, Huntington, New York: Robert E. Krieger, 1977.
- [8] Widrow, Bernard and Stearns, Samuel Adaptive Signal Processing, Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey: Prentice Hall, 1985.
- [9] Widrow, B. and others "Adaptive Antenna Systems," Proceedings of the IEEE, 55, No. 12, 2143-2159 (December 1967).
- [10] Widrow, Bernard and others "The Complex LMS Algorithm," Proceedings of the IEEE, 63, No.4, 719-720 (April 1975).

Figure 2: BOSS Discrete LMS Loop

Figure 3: Two element array [4, 24]

Figure 1: BOSS Analog LMS Loop

SIGNAL SECTION

O# 1 OUTPUT OF ARRAY
O# 2 OUTPUT OF SECOND ELEMENT

Figure 4: BOSS Two Element Array Signal Section

O# 1 OUTPUT TO FIRST ELEMENT
O# 2 SECOND ELEMENT OUTPUT

Figure 5: BOSS Two Element Array

Figure 6: BOSS LMS Test Circuit

Figure 7: LMS Test Circuit Weight with $\mu = 0.1$

Figure 8: LMS Test Circuit Weight with $\mu = 0.05$

Figure 9: BOSS Two Element Array LMS System

Figure 10: Two Element Array Weights with Source at 0 Degrees

Figure 11: BOSS Complex LMS Test Circuit

Figure 12: BOSS Applebaum Test Circuit

Complex Magnitude

Figure 13: Complex Weight Magnitude - Applebaum Algorithm

Complex Phase

Figure 14: Complex Weight Phase - Applebaum Algorithm

Figure 15: Array Gain - Jammer at 10 Degrees